

Philippine Foundation
for Equity in Health

Beyond Fragmentation: Understanding Primary Health Care in the Guimaras Unified Health Network

*A Comprehensive Assessment of the Guimaras Unified
Health Network Primary Care Facility Capacities*

FINAL ASSESSMENT REPORT

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This report presents findings from a comprehensive mixed-methods assessment of primary care facility capacities, patient experiences, and community perspectives within the Guimaras Unified Health Network, providing evidence-based recommendations for strengthening primary health care delivery in small island health system contexts.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Background and Objective

The Universal Health Care (UHC) Law aims to provide all Filipinos with equitable access to quality and affordable health care services, with Primary Care Facilities (PCFs) serving as the first contact of care and navigator for higher-level services when needed. However, PCFs continue to face challenges in coverage, access, and quality, particularly in geographically isolated settings. This comprehensive assessment evaluated the five primary care facilities within the Guimaras Unified Health Network (GUHN) to determine their actual capacities to deliver primary health care services and generate evidence-based recommendations for strengthening the network's ability to provide equitable, people-centered, and safe primary health care to all Guimarasnons.

Methodology

The assessment employed a mixed-methods approach combining facility capacity assessments, patient experience documentation, and community stakeholder engagement. Primary data collection included: (1) Primary Care Facility Assessment Tool (PCF-AT) administered across all five facilities, (2) patient surveys with 96 respondents, (3) patient journey documentation with 11 cases, and (4) engagement with a 10-member Community Advisory Group. The evaluation utilized systems thinking principles to understand interconnections, feedback loops, and emergent properties within the GUHN that conventional facility-based assessments would miss.

Key Findings

Strong Foundational Elements: Guimaras demonstrates solid groundwork for UHC implementation with 80% PhilHealth coverage, universal Konsulta accreditation across all PCFs, adequate physician deployment, and consistently high patient satisfaction scores averaging 4.2 across all domains. The province's robust community health infrastructure, anchored by 766 barangay health workers, provides strong social capital for health system development.

Critical System Gaps: Despite ₱184.71M in province-wide health investment for primary health care, systematic strategic purchasing deficiencies prevent comprehensive service delivery. Specialized health programs register zero PhilHealth claims across all PCFs despite facilities actively providing TB treatment, family planning, and maternal care services. The documented geographic premium averaging ₱272.50 per visit, with 35% of patients facing moderate-to-catastrophic expenses, creates systematic financial protection failures. Information system fragmentation across multiple platforms burdens staff with redundant data entry while preventing evidence-based planning necessary for integrated care coordination.

Service Delivery Challenges: Only three of five facilities have achieved DOH licensing as PCFs, with infrastructure requirements creating barriers for San Lorenzo and Sibunag RHUs. All facilities lack licensed pharmacies and clinical laboratories, relying on outsourcing arrangements with private providers and hospitals that create additional costs and delays for patients. Private providers demonstrate mixed engagement with Konsulta service delivery, with private clinics and hospitals showing 36% and 39% service conversion rates respectively, while patients registered to private providers frequently seek care at PCFs, creating uncompensated service delivery. Workforce gaps include absent pharmacists across all facilities and dependence on contractual nursing staff, creating precarious foundations for sustainable service delivery.

Quality-Access Trade-offs: Patient data reveals that quality factors drive facility selection decisions more than accessibility considerations, with 41% prioritizing quality of care over proximity. However, this quality-driven preference may exclude vulnerable populations who cannot absorb transportation costs ranging from ₱0-₱200 per visit, potentially perpetuating health inequities.

Strategic Implications

The assessment reveals a fundamental paradox: GUHN possesses strong foundational elements for UHC implementation but faces systemic barriers that national frameworks do not adequately address. The documented strategic purchasing deficiencies, regulatory misalignments, and geographic cost premiums indicate that successful UHC implementation in small island contexts requires systematic adaptation of national UHC frameworks that acknowledge and address unique challenges. Community governance capacity in Guimaras often exceeds mainland contexts, providing opportunities for sophisticated health system stewardship that current frameworks underutilize.

Recommendations

The assessment recommends implementing an **Innovation Prototyping Framework** that transforms documented challenges into testable solutions through iterative design, stakeholder co-creation, and evidence-based adaptation across three interconnected prototype tracks:

Prototype Track 1: Integrated Service Delivery Network - Re-designing network-based service delivery models that coordinate fragmented facility-based care through hub-and-spoke coordination, unified patient care pathways, mobile service integration, and shared resource optimization.

Prototype Track 2: Community-Responsive Health Governance - Designing governance mechanisms that enable meaningful community participation through community health system stewardship, real-time feedback integration, traditional-modern health integration, and community health financing innovation.

Prototype Track 3: Sustainable Island Health Financing - Developing financing mechanisms that address unique island cost structures through network-based strategic purchasing, integrated external service financing, and geographic risk adjustment.

Conclusion and Future Directions

This assessment establishes that small island health systems can achieve UHC goals but require fundamental innovations in service delivery, governance, and financing rather than simple adaptation of mainland models. The GUHN is positioned to serve as a learning site for developing and testing innovative approaches that can be scaled to other island contexts throughout the Philippines. The prototyping implementation strategy employs a human-centered design that emphasizes stakeholder co-creation, rapid testing, and iterative refinement. Success in Guimaras will provide validated models for delivering equitable, people-centered primary healthcare while demonstrating how technical assistance can evolve from conventional implementation support to collaborative innovation partnerships that generate actionable insights for health system strengthening.

BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

The Universal Health Care (UHC) Law represents a transformative initiative to establish equitable healthcare access for all Filipinos, yet significant implementation challenges persist. The UHC Law aims to build and strengthen the Philippines' local health system to provide all Filipinos with equitable access to quality and affordable health care services. Primary Care Facilities (PCFs) play a vital role in achieving UHC by serving as the first contact of care for individuals seeking health services and as a navigator for higher or inpatient care when needed. However, PCFs continue to have limited coverage, access, and quality. Health information data access is also fragmented and is a hurdle to the province-wide efforts of integrating health resources. Consequently, primary health care services remain underutilized as spending for preventive care and outpatient services at the primary care level is significantly less compared to hospital-based care.

Guimaras province has demonstrated strong commitment to UHC implementation but continues to face unique healthcare challenges due to its geographic isolation, limited population coverage, and financial constraints that hinder optimal service delivery. Guimaras, a second class island province and a committed UHC Integration Site since 2019, has made efforts to implement and operationalize the technical, managerial, and financial integration aspects of the UHC law. These strategies were applied to an integrated network of health system managers, service providers, and local government leaders in the province called the Guimaras Unified Health Network (GUHN). Improving access to health services and reaching target health investments is a challenge for the province, wherein local governments mainly finance health services using tax-share transfers from the national government. Aside from national tax allocations, health facilities also receive assistance from the Department of Health (DOH), which remain largely unutilized. Challenges in accreditation hinder the facilities from accessing PhilHealth payments as a supplemental fund source for health. With a grounded and nuanced understanding of the Guimarasnons' health needs and the continuous efforts of the GUHN to strengthen service delivery and financing mechanisms within the network, investments for health and utilization of health services, especially at the primary care level can still be improved.

Our intervention focused on generating evidence on network and facility capacity in providing primary health care services and document patient experience in accessing care. We conducted an assessment of the five (5) primary care facilities in the province of Guimaras with a focus on the following areas: a) health service coverage and access, b) health service delivery, and c) health financing. Through this exercise, we sought to determine the actual capacities of the facilities to uphold their LGU Code mandate to deliver primary health care. The assessment looked into compliance of facilities with DOH licensing and PhilHealth accreditation standards, and also captured the facilitating factors and barriers in operationalizing the policies and issuances for health. Client-side experiences were also captured through patient surveys and interviews documenting patient experiences in accessing health services. The assessment exercise sought to meet the following objectives of the project:

- Determine the actual capacities of health facilities based on DOH licensing and PhilHealth accreditation standards.
- Capture health facility staff perspectives on service provision and delivery.
- Document client/patient experiences in accessing health services and ascertain their awareness and expectations in terms of health.
- Generate recommendations to maximize current facility capacities and inform network-level arrangements to strategically improve primary health care service delivery and access within the province.

METHODOLOGY

This exercise employed a mixed-methods approach to assess the capacities of primary care facilities in delivering primary healthcare and capture the client perception of access to care.

Quantitative data were collected through a self-administered PCF Assessment Tool and patient surveys. In addition to this, key informant interviews (KIIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs) with patients and health staff were also conducted. Secondary data collection was also done through a review of relevant laws and policies, and an analysis of data sets relevant to primary health care.

PCF Assessment Tool (PCF-AT)

We developed a PCF Assessment Tool (Annex A) to capture the available services and capacities of health workers in a facility based on the standards and guidelines issued by DOH and PhilHealth. The process of developing the tool was guided by relevant policies from the Department of Health and PhilHealth, and reviewed by the team. The tool was distributed to all five (5) facilities for self-assessment, followed by a site visit by the team for data validation. Data validation was also supported with data analysis of secondary data from PhilHealth, DOH, and the PHO.

Patient Survey

A patient survey tool (Annex B) was designed to measure the client perspective in accessing healthcare services. The tool gathered information about the patient's health-seeking behavior, their awareness of and satisfaction with the facility's services, and their awareness of PhilHealth's benefits. The survey was administered to a sample of fifteen (15) to twenty (23) patients in each facility, with a total of 96 respondents. The same tool was also administered to members of the Community Advisory Group (CAG) to gauge the perception of community leaders and sectoral representatives in terms of health services they access. A total of ten (10) responses were recorded from the CAG.

Patient Journey Documentation

The assessment exercise also documented patient pathways and facility processes when accessing health services. We identified two (2) patients¹ in every facility and interviewed them using a patient journey documentation tool (Annex C) designed by the team. The interview covered the entire duration of a patient's visit in the facility. A total of ten (11) respondents were interviewed for this aspect of the assessment.

Quantitative data collected from primary data collection activities were encoded and consolidated in a data sheet and processed accordingly. Both the PCF AT and Patient Surveys were self-administered while the Patient Journey was administered through an assisted interview. Preliminary results of the PCF AT were presented to the health facility staff to validate the results. The data were also shared with key stakeholders from PhilHealth, Provincial DOH, and the Provincial Health Office to generate province-wide strategies and recommendations for the network. Participation in all interviews was voluntary, and consent was obtained from the respective agencies and respondents for all data collection activities conducted. Document structuring and analytical framework development were supported by Claude (Anthropic AI) while all data collection, analysis, and interpretation remained under the direct control of the researchers.

¹ A total of three (3) patients were interviewed from Nueva Valencia PCF.

RESULTS

PART 1: PRIMARY CARE FACILITY ASSESSMENT

While Guimaras province has made notable progress in establishing primary care infrastructure, significant operational and systemic challenges impede the delivery of effective universal health coverage. This assessment of the five primary care facilities in the province reveals that despite three facilities achieving DOH licensing and all maintaining PhilHealth accreditation for consultation services, critical gaps persist in service utilization, workforce adequacy, and information management. Key findings include low Konsulta registration and utilization rates, chronic workforce shortages in specialized positions, and fragmented information systems that burden staff with redundant data entry. These challenges collectively underscore the urgent need for strategic interventions to optimize primary healthcare delivery and strengthen the foundation for universal health coverage implementation.

Facility Licensing and Accreditation

A primary care facility is defined as an institution that primarily delivers individual and population-based primary care services, which shall be licensed or registered by the DOH. These primary care services include medical consultations, minor surgical services, and ancillary services. The first two services must be available in-house, while ancillary services (birthing services, dental services, clinical laboratory, ambulance service, and pharmacy) may be outsourced to other facilities through a memorandum of agreement or service-level agreement. PhilHealth accredits these PCFs for services provided, according to available benefit packages. The Konsultasyon Sulit at Tama (Konsulta) benefit package covers the primary care services covering essential laboratory, pharmaceutical and consultation services within a PCF. Aside from Konsulta, PhilHealth also offers benefit packages for selected outpatient services within the PCFs such as maternity and birthing services, animal bite treatments, family planning services, and tuberculosis treatment.

At the time of assessment, there are three DOH-licensed primary care facilities (PCF) in Guimaras province, namely, Buenavista PCF 1, Jordan PCF, and Nueva Valencia PCF. Table 1 shows the DOH licensing status of each facility and its corresponding ancillary services expected in a PCF. The three licensed PCFs are also licensed birthing facilities and dental laboratories. All five facilities have no licensed pharmacies, ambulance, and clinical laboratories and signed a contract with partner facilities to comply with the licensing and accreditation requirements. However, all five facilities continue to provide maternal care, basic laboratory tests, and dispensing of medicines, subject to availability of supplies and commodities (Figure 1, conditional in-house provision). Partner facilities identified are DOH-licensed private facilities within the municipality or hospitals within the province.

Table 1: DOH licensing and PhilHealth accreditation status of Guimaras primary care facilities.

	Buenavista PCF	Jordan PCF	Nueva Valencia PCF	San Lorenzo RHU	Sibunag RHU
DOH License to Operate (data as of January 2025)					
Primary Care Facility	✓	✓	✓		
Birthing Facility	✓	✓	✓		
Clinical Laboratory					
Dental Laboratory	✓	✓	✓		
Pharmacy					
Ambulance					
Diagnostic and Imaging Services (ECG, ultrasound, x-ray)	✓ (ECG and x-ray)				
PhilHealth Accreditation (data as of February 2025)					
Konsulta Package Provider	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Maternity Care Package Provider			✓		
Animal Bite Package Provider					
Family Planning Provider					
TB DOTS Provider		on process	✓	✓	

Figure 1: Availability and provision of ancillary services (birthing, dental, laboratory, pharmaceutical, diagnostic & imaging) in Guimaras primary care facilities.

Infrastructure deficiencies and licensing requirements of ancillary services hinder the licensing process of facilities as a primary care facility. A major bottleneck in facilitating the licensing process of facilities is the physical infrastructure of the facilities which require compliance to the standard floor plan and room partitions set by DOH. The three licensed facilities were able to work around their current facility structure and comply with these requirements, but San Lorenzo RHU and Sibunag RHU require renovations to be made before they can process their LTO. According to the staff in both facilities, the cost of renovations will be covered by their DOH Health Facility Enhancement Program (HFEP) grants. Delays in the awarding of funds and imposed moratorium for big LGU projects during the election has hampered the commencement of the construction process, and affected the timelines in processing their respective LTOs. Both facilities were also advised to process their birthing facilities licenses together with the PCF licenses.

PhilHealth accreditation as providers for applicable benefit packages varies across the five PCFs. Primary care facilities are eligible to apply for accreditation as providers for selected benefit packages including Konsulta, the primary care benefit package, and other outpatient benefit packages such as the maternity care package (MCP), animal bite treatment package, family planning package, and Tuberculosis Directly Observed Treatment Short-course (TBDOTS) package. Accredited facilities are then eligible to receive payments through reimbursement mechanisms from PhilHealth as determined by their PhilHealth accreditation for each benefit package. During the assessment period, all five facilities are accredited Konsulta providers (Table 1). Among the three licensed birthing facilities, only Nueva Valencia is accredited as an MCP provider which only qualifies the said facility to be reimbursed for every facility-based delivery. Treatment for tuberculosis (TBDOTS) is another benefit package that can be availed in PCFs. Nueva Valencia and San Lorenzo are the only accredited TBDOTS providers during assessment while Jordan is in the process of complying with accreditation requirements.

Population Coverage

The PhilHealth membership data for Guimaras province reveals variations in healthcare coverage across its five municipalities. Buenavista and Jordan demonstrate the highest membership rates at 85% and 86% respectively (Table 2). These two municipalities also represent the largest populations, with Buenavista serving 53,005 residents and Jordan covering 40,903 people. In contrast, San Lorenzo shows the lowest PhilHealth membership rate at 71%, with only 21,672 of its 30,327 residents enrolled in the program. Nueva Valencia and Sibunag fall in the middle range with enrollment rates of 79% and 74% respectively. Overall, the province achieves an 80% PhilHealth membership rate, falling below the membership coverage of 87% in Western Visayas and 91% in the entire country. These numbers highlight the need for targeted enrollment campaigns and streamlining efforts in healthcare service delivery to locate and register the remaining 37,613 Guimarasnons who are not yet PhilHealth members.

Table 2: PhilHealth membership status in the Province of Guimaras
(PhilHealth Guimaras Data as of February 2025)

MUNICIPALITY	Projected Catchment Population (2024)	PhilHealth Membership	
		Count	% of Pop'n
BUENAVISTA	53,005	45,225	85%
JORDAN	40,903	35,076	86%
NUEVA VALENCIA	43,220	34,029	79%
SAN LORENZO	30,327	21,672	71%
SIBUNAG	23,582	17,416	74%
TOTAL	191,037	153,418	80%

There are discrepancies in the municipal counts of individuals belonging to the different vulnerable population segments and PhilHealth enrollment figures which impacts the coverage for the provision of social services, including health. PhilHealth coverage for senior citizens in Guimaras is broad with the number of enrolled members exceeding the count of the respective local government units suggesting that PhilHealth has a more complete record of individuals over the age of 60 compared to the registries maintained by the Office of Senior Citizen Affairs (OSCA) in each LGU (Table 3). Municipal-level PWD count on the other hand is higher than the registered PhilHealth membership under the PWD category. The consultation with PhilHealth Regional Office clarified that their PWD registry is based on the DOH Philippine Registry For Persons With Disabilities (PRPWD) which constantly encounters challenges in encoding data into the system. Furthermore, PhilHealth explained that the PWD membership type does not reflect all PWDs since they may also be categorized under other membership types, depending on their employment status. Indigenous people do not have a specific membership type and may be categorized under indigents, NHTS, or other PhilHealth membership types as well. Recognizing the inconsistency of data from reporting units, health facility staff, specifically the barangay health workers (BHWs) and midwives, conduct annual household profiling activities to capture actual population groups. The household profiles of the entire catchment population is then used as a basis for health service delivery of the facility.

Table 3: PhilHealth membership of vulnerable population segments in Guimaras Province
(2025 PhilHealth Data; MLGU Data).

MUNICIPALITY	Vulnerable Population Count and PhilHealth Membership					
	LGU-registered Senior Citizens	Lifetime & Senior Citizen PhilHealth Members	LGU-registered PWD	Persons with Disability PhilHealth Members	NCIP-registered Indigenous People	4Ps/NHTS/FI / Others PhilHealth Members
BUENAVISTA	No Data	9,482	No Data	16	216	No disaggregation of PhilHealth members belonging to the IP
JORDAN	4,989	7,139	610	48	502	
NUEVA VALENCIA	5,056	7,953	807	269	214	
SAN LORENZO	3,613	3,502	642	8	0	
SIBUNAG	3,185	3,702	524	7	295	
TOTAL	16,843	31,778	2,583	348	1,227	

Data sources: (1) IP Data: NCIP, (2) Senior Citizens: OSCA, (3) PWD: MSWDO

Konsulta registration is not yet maximized in the province with only 46% of Guimarasnons registered to a Konsulta facility (Figure 2). Enrollment to PhilHealth is a prerequisite before an individual can be registered to a Konsulta facility and be eligible to access the primary care benefit packages entitled to each member. At the time of assessment, only 88,150 Guimarasnons are registered to a Konsulta provider. A total of 52,931 individuals accounting for 28% of the provincial population are registered to one of the five PCFs in the province. Nueva Valencia and Buenavista are the forerunners in the number of individuals registered as a Konsulta beneficiary within their facility. To increase registration, PhilHealth supported the PCFs by facilitating the auto-registration for select

membership types: senior citizens and indigents. Additionally, PhilHealth provides a list of all clients that are registered in a Konsulta facility.

Figure 2. Percentage of Guimaras population registered to the PhilHealth Konsulta program (PhilHealth 2024).

Service Utilization

Konsulta facilities show limited success in converting Konsulta registrations to service delivery. Primary Care Facilities demonstrate variable but generally low service delivery rates, with Buenavista PCF leading among primary care providers by serving 3,322 individuals (31% of its registered population), while Jordan PCF shows significantly lower performance with only 1,070 FPE services provided (19% conversion rate) as shown in Figure 3. Nueva Valencia PCF, despite having the highest number of registered individuals, achieved only a 12% service delivery rate (2,133 out of 17,667 registrations). Conversely, Sibunag RHU was able to provide FPE to 64% of its registered population, the highest among all five PCFs.

Public hospitals and private providers show mixed engagement with Konsulta service delivery. The two public hospitals in the province - Buenavista Emergency Hospital (BEH) and Dr. Catalino Gallego Nava Provincial Hospital (DCGNPH)² collectively registered a total of 21,024 individuals but only provided health services to 69 clients. There is a notable similarity in the performance of private clinics and the lone private hospital in the province in terms of converting Konsulta registrations to first patient encounters, providing health services to 36% and 39% of its registered population, respectively. Interviews with PCF staff also revealed that patients who are registered to a private provider or public hospital still frequent the primary care facilities to seek medical consultations due to proximity from their residence, which the PCFs also cater. This has impacts on the financing standpoint, incurring losses to the PCFs catering to these patients who are registered to a different Konsulta facility (DCGNMC, BEH, Private). This outcome defeats the purpose of the Konsulta program which supports the mandate of the UHC law to assign every individual to a primary care provider who will then receive reimbursement for services provided to each registered individual.

² DCGNPH has been renamed to Dr. Catalino Gallego Nava Medical Center (DCGNMC) since March 2025.

Figure 3. Number of Konsulta-registered individuals provided with First Patient Encounter (PhilHealth 2024).

Healthcare facilities in Guimaras demonstrate significant variation in the number of medical consultations done (Figure 4). There is a three-fold difference between the highest and lowest performers. Nueva Valencia PCF handled the highest consultation volume with 6,386 cases, representing nearly 23% of all consultations across the five facilities, followed by Buenavista PCF (5,605) and San Lorenzo RHU (5,092), which together account for another 39% of total cases. Jordan PCF had significantly lower utilization at 2,751 consultations, while Sibunag RHU reported the lowest at 3,171 cases.

Figure 4. Number of consultations and referrals made by each PCF for 2024 (DOH FHSIS M1 Reports and Facility Referral Reports 2024).

Outgoing referrals across facilities account for 2-3% of their consultations, suggesting varying levels of clinical cases catered and facility capacity to handle advanced cases. Nueva Valencia, despite having the highest consultation volume, maintained a relatively low referral rate (170 outgoing referrals, roughly 3% of total consultations). In contrast, Buenavista had a higher referral rate (119 referrals from 5,605 consultations, about 2%), suggesting different case complexity or facility capacity constraints. Referred cases are mostly medical and surgical in nature and were referred out to either public or private hospitals in the provinces. Notably, Nueva Valencia, San Lorenzo, and Sibunag facilities had a number of animal bite cases referred to DCGNMC and BEH, the only public animal bite treatment centers (ABTC) in the province. Buenavista PCF and Jordan PCF have no reported

referrals for animal bites. The location of both ABTC facilities could explain client behavior since both facilities are also located in the municipalities of Jordan and Buenavista, and clients from both municipalities needing treatment for animal bites go directly to these facilities without needing to be referred by the PCFs in the area. Complex pregnancy cases are also appropriately referred to higher level facilities.

The morbidity profile of Guimaras shows that facilities in the province are handling both acute and chronic diseases. The top 10 morbidity causes shown in Table 4 reveal a typical primary care pattern dominated by respiratory infections (acute upper respiratory infections and pneumonia), chronic conditions (hypertension, diabetes, heart disease), and infectious diseases (tuberculosis, urinary tract infections). Management of acute cases such as respiratory infections, wounds, allergies, etc requires sufficient medical and pharmaceutical supplies for timely treatment. Chronic diseases on the other hand open opportunities for proactive health promotion of healthier lifestyle accompanied by sufficient medication supply.

Table 4. Top 10 causes of morbidity in Guimaras in all ages (DOH FHSIS Report 2024)

TEN LEADING CAUSES OF MORBIDITY	
1.	Acute Upper Respiratory Infection (J00-J06)
2.	Pneumonia (J18)
3.	Urinary Tract Infection (N00-N39)
4.	Hypertensive Heart Disease, HCVD (I11)
5.	Hypertension (I10)
6.	Tuberculosis (A15-A19)
7.	Allergy/Hypersensitivity Reaction (T78.4)
8.	Skin Diseases (L00-L99)
9.	Wounds/Injuries (S00-S99)
10.	Diabetes Mellitus (E10-E14)

Data quality issues may be compromising the accuracy of reported healthcare utilization statistics due to underreported cases. Interviews with health workers revealed that FHSIS M2 reports do not accurately reflect actual consultation numbers due to iClinicSys encoding backlogs indicating potential data quality issues. Reports for referrals made also incur delays due to the volume of tasks catered by the facility staff. As a result, true service utilization and referred cases is actually higher than reported and documented.

Health Workforce

The deployment of core PCF staff demonstrates adequate physician coverage but reveals gaps in other cadres that threaten the foundation of primary health care delivery. All five facilities have successfully filled the positions for their municipal health officers. At least one rural health physician is also available to cater medical consults, with Buenavista PCF leading with three physicians (3:53,005 total population), followed by Nueva Valencia PCF with two physicians (2:43,220 total population), and the remaining facilities each maintaining one physician (Figure 5). However, this number is not adequate based on the HRH to population set by DOH of 1 doctor for every 20,000 population. LGU-hired contractual nurses and DOH-deployed nurses significantly augment the nurses in each facility to meet the 1:10,000 DOH standard. Among the five PCFs, Sibunag RHU is the only facility with no public health nurse, hence the adequacy of nurses are mainly because of contractual personnel and nurses deployed under the Nurse Deployment Program (NDP). This glaring dependence on non-permanent employees can pose a problem to facility management and service provision since nurses serve as the primary data managers and play crucial roles in both preventive care and chronic disease management. The midwife positions appear adequately staffed across all facilities, suggesting that barangay health stations have sufficient manpower to continue service delivery at the community level.

	HRH CADRE	BUENAVISTA PCF	JORDAN PCF	NUEVA VALENCIA PCF	SAN LORENZO RHU	SIBUNAG RHU
CORE	Municipal Health Officer					
	Rural Health Physician	3 : 53,005	1 : 40,903	2 : 43,220	1 : 30,327	1 : 23,582
	Nurse					
	Midwife					
	Sanitary Inspector					
ANCILLARY	Pharmacist					
	Dentist					
	Dental Aide					
	Medical Technologist					
	Lab Aide					
	Ambulance Driver					
ADMIN	IT Officer					
	Records Officer					
	Admin Officer					
EXTENSION	Barangay Health Worker					
	Barangay Nutrition Scholar					

■ ACHIEVED |
 ■ DID NOT MEET STANDARD |
 ■ NO HRH ASSIGNED |
 ■ DESIGNATE

Figure 5. Status of health worker adequacy in PCFs based on DOH-required cadres.

Pharmacist positions remain unfilled across all facilities relying on outsourcing of pharmaceutical services to partner facilities. The limitations on the hiring of LGU personnel (PS Cap) hinders the hiring of plantilla personnel to fill the pharmacist position and potential candidates are also uninterested to work as contractual employees. In order to facilitate the delivery of pharmaceutical services and comply with DOH PCF licensing and PhilHealth Konsulta accreditation requirements, PCFs outsourced the dispensing of medicines to private pharmacies or hospitals. Basic medicines and vitamins are continually dispensed at the PCF and RHU level, subject to the availability of medicine supply and with the oversight of nurses. Health workers are aware of the policies surrounding the dispensing of medicines but choose to continue with the practice because from experience, patients would not follow through with their medications if they were sent to a different pharmacy after consultation.

The employment status of other cadres providing ancillary, administrative, and extension services varies per facility. Buenavista PCF has hired a dentist on contractual status while Nueva Valencia PCF and Jordan PCF have a plantilla-hired dentist. This allows for the regularity of in-house service provision, albeit appointments being scheduled and made in advance. Meanwhile, dental services in San Lorenzo and Sibunag RHUs are provided by one DOH-deployed dentist who goes on rotation duty between the two facilities. Three out of the five facilities - Buenavista PCF, Jordan PCF, and Sibunag RHU have filled in plantilla positions for medical technologists while Nueva Valencia PCF and Jordan RHU have medical technologists on duty under contractual / DOH-deployed status. They provide routine laboratory services (urinalysis, fecalysis, blood typing, CBC, etc) in their respective facilities, as long as reagents and medical supplies are available. Filling up administrative positions in the facilities are done either by hiring a specific personnel for the position or designating an existing health worker to take on this additional role. San Lorenzo RHU have yet to fill in the positions for records and admin officers. These findings show that facilities take on different strategies in filling up the required positions to comply with licensing and accreditation requirements. Factors that affect these strategies hinge on the availability of plantilla positions within the LGU, and decisions of facility heads on which positions or cadres to prioritize.

Barangay health workers (BHW) who serve as the extension of the health system to the community represent the strongest component of the local health workforce. A total of 766 BHWs across all the municipalities are the primary links between formal health facilities and community members, providing basic health education, preventive services, and referral support. The large number of BHWs suggests strong community engagement and provides opportunities for comprehensive health promotion activities, disease prevention programs, and early identification of health problems at the grassroots level. Barangay health workers also play a significant role in conducting household profiling activities and updating of population masterlists to guide health planning and program implementation.

The regional healthcare system faces workforce gaps and training deficiencies that collectively undermine comprehensive primary healthcare delivery, requiring immediate strategic intervention at the province or network level. The absence of technical health staff across all facilities resulted in the reliance on partner providers to provide the services. Training data reveals strong coverage in maternal and child health competencies (all five facilities trained in BEMONC and Family Planning) and basic emergency care, but significant deficiencies in specialized areas including limited adolescent health care capacity and near-complete absence of mental health training (MHGAP available only in San Lorenzo). By practice, the PHO program coordinators take stock of the training and refresher course needs of health workers in all public health facilities in Guimaras and coordinate with the program manager of the Department of Health CHD, who then facilitates the actual training. However, training needs and refresher courses needed by health workers tend to be overlooked due to a multitude of tasks expected on a daily basis, affecting the capacity and confidence of facility staff to provide expected services. Validation interviews also surfaced that the rapid staff turnover and competing program commitments further undermine service continuity and negate training investments. The facility and the network as a whole must work on solutions to streamline capacity building activities and create strategies to boost health worker morale.

Information Management

All five PCFs in Guimaras use a hybrid information management system that involves the maintenance of both physical and electronic health records. Different tools are used to maintain these records such as an individual treatment record (ITR) which contains information about a patient's medical consultation history, a target client list (TCL) which lists important information about a specific population subgroup within a facility's catchment population, and several logbooks containing a line list of daily consultation cases and referrals made. These paper-based reports are then encoded into different health information systems required by the DOH and PhilHealth. Data from these records are also used to inform planning and investment strategies for health.

The province's information management suffers from a fragmented technology landscape where multiple specialized systems operate in isolation. Guimaras province is implementing iClinicSys as the universal electronic medical record (EMR) system across all five primary care facilities. Adopting one EMR at the primary care level ensures consistency in data collection, patient record management, and operational procedures throughout the province. Encoders of each health facility are also expected to input data and submit reports to separate health information systems (HIS) and digital platforms such as the PIDSR, ITIS, and FHSIS to comply with program-based reporting (Figure 6). Aside from report submission, filing of PhilHealth claims involves a separate system - eKonsulta for the Konsulta benefit package and eClaims for the other benefit packages. There have been efforts to streamline encoding and submission processes for Konsulta claims by creating an eKonsulta module in the iClinicSys EMR to address the issue of multiple encoding, but health workers still opt to separately encode data into the iClinicSys and eKonsulta after hearing reviews of delayed posting and lost data upon upload. The unreliability of system upgrades and limitation of systems in terms of interoperability forces health workers to perform redundant data entry

tasks when generating reports, undermining the potential benefits of digital health information systems.

Figure 6. Map of health information flow and relationship of data to health and investment planning in Guimaras PCFs.

Integrated health information systems serve as the foundation for evidence-based health planning and strategic resource allocation. When healthcare facilities operate with standardized platforms like iClinicSys and maintain interoperable data collection methods, health officials gain access to comprehensive, real-time information that allows them to identify emerging health trends, track disease patterns, and allocate scarce resources with precision. Conversely, Guimaras' experience with fragmented systems demonstrates the consequences of poor data infrastructure. The ongoing struggle of PCFs with manual and electronic record-keeping systems illustrates how poor data management can systematically undermine both health planning effectiveness and investment returns. When facilities rely on paper-based systems that process information significantly slower than real-time encoding capabilities, health planners lose the critical ability to monitor disease outbreaks as they develop, track treatment outcomes across populations, or assess program effectiveness during implementation phases. These technological silos prevent planners from developing a complete epidemiological picture of facility and network health needs, forcing them to make resource allocation decisions based on incomplete information rather than evidence-based analysis. The experience in information management of PCFs in Guimaras province opens a big potential for functional data systems to enable provincial health planners to make informed decisions and make sound investments that provide maximum public health impact.

HEALTH FINANCING

Healthcare budget allocation in this Philippine province demonstrates significant funding disparities and centralized resource distribution patterns that may impact equitable service delivery across local government units. The total LGU health budgets vary considerably, with Buenavista PCF receiving the highest allocation at ₱18.36 million, followed by Nueva Valencia PCF at ₱16.56 million, while Sibunag RHU receives the lowest at ₱10.81 million (Table 5). A notable pattern emerges in the distribution of DOH assistance, where only Sibunag RHU receives cash assistance (₱1.43 million) while the Provincial Health Office receives a substantially larger amount (₱38.82 million). The municipal cash assistance to Sibunag is for the hazard allowances of health workers who were on duty during the pandemic. Additionally, DOH assistance data for the other four municipalities were not available. The Provincial Health Office also receives the largest share of DOH In-Kind

Assistance at ₱54.67 million, suggesting a centralized approach to DOH funding distribution. The province-wide total of ₱184.71 million demonstrates substantial healthcare investment, though the uneven distribution pattern may reflect varying population sizes, health needs, or administrative capacities across the different health facilities.

Table 5. Primary care financing for health (2024).

	BUENAVISTA PCF	JORDAN PCF	NUEVA VALENCIA PCF	SAN LORENZO RHU	SIBUNAG RHU	PROVINCIAL HEALTH OFFICE
Total LGU Budget for Health (MHO Annual Budget/ MLGU data)	₱18,363,900.00	₱14,831,500.00	₱16,557,724.00	₱12,456,805.93	₱10,811,652.52	-
DOH Cash Assistance (MLGU FURs, CSF)	-	-	-	-	₱1,429,000.00	₱38,817,163.00
DOH In-Kind Assistance (Indicative amount)	₱0.00	₱0.00	₱0.00	₱0.00	₱0.00	₱54,667,251.68
Konsulta Claims	₱4,655,280.00	₱1,981,520.00	₱4,144,600.00	₱3,185,800.00	₱2,811,120.00	-
MCP Claims	-	-	-	-	-	-
TBDOTS Claims	-	-	-	-	-	-
FP Claims	₱0.00	₱0.00	₱0.00	₱0.00	₱0.00	-
ABTC Claims	₱0.00	₱0.00	₱0.00	₱0.00	₱0.00	-
HIV Claims	-	-	-	-	-	-
Province-wide TOTAL			₱184,713,317.13			

Data sources: PhilHealth Claims Data, Department of Health Terms of Partnership, LGU Annual Budget Report, LGU Fund Utilization Reports for 2024.

The PhilHealth claims data for various healthcare programs reveals uneven service delivery patterns across facilities, with primary care programs showing robust utilization while specialized health services demonstrate concerning gaps in implementation or accessibility.

Resources from PhilHealth are accessed through reimbursement mechanisms where accredited facilities are paid for services they deliver that are covered by existing benefit packages. Konsulta Claims, representing primary care consultations, generate substantial reimbursements across all facilities, ranging from ₱1.98 million at Jordan PCF to ₱4.66 million at Buenavista PCF, indicating that basic healthcare services are actively being accessed throughout the province. However, the remaining specialized health programs show alarming patterns of underutilization since none of the PCFs are PhilHealth accredited providers. While basic consultations are readily available and patients have access to treatments for tuberculosis, maternal health, family planning, and other critical health services that require more specialized resources or training, facilities are not paid for services rendered. All five PCFs did not receive any payment from PhilHealth for MCP and TBDOTS services delivered. Similarly, FP Claims and ABTC Claims both show zero values across all facilities, since the PhilHealth accredited FP providers in the province are DCGNPH and private clinics. Animal bites are also catered in private clinics or province-owned facilities - BEH and DCGNPH. The stark contrast between the robust Konsulta program utilization and the complete absence of specialized program claims indicates the lack of accredited facilities at the primary care level.

PART 2: PATIENT EXPERIENCE

This comprehensive assessment integrates findings from two complementary data collection tools examining patient experiences across the five PCFs. The analysis combines quantitative population estimates from 96 patient surveys with qualitative operational insights from 11 detailed patient journey assessments, supplemented by perspectives from 10 Community Advisory Group (CAG) members, providing a robust evidence base for health system strengthening within the GUHN. The integration hierarchy prioritizes survey tools for population-level prevalence data, while patient journey documentation leads operational process understanding with real-time validation, and perspectives from the CAG reveal community needs independent of current utilization patterns. This ensures

comprehensive coverage across all five GUHN municipalities with 100% facility participation and mixed-methods triangulation for data validation.

Patient Survey: Demographic Distribution and Health-Seeking Behavior

Patient demographic analysis from the survey sample (n=96) demonstrates comprehensive network representation with a mean age of 44 ranging from 15-91 years (Table 6). The survey population is distributed across the following age groups: 3% adolescents (10-19), 75% adults (20-59), and 18% elderly (60+). The remaining 4% did not indicate their age. The survey population is predominantly female (71%) which reflects a pattern in healthcare decision-making throughout Guimaras Province. Facility specific demographic variations reveal that Nueva Valencia PCF exhibited notably higher female representation at 94% compared to the network average. Age patterns on the other hand ranges from Jordan PCF’s younger population (average age is 38) to the older demographic of Sibunag RHU with a mean age of 51.

Table 6: Demographics of Facility Survey Respondents

Facility	Sample Size	Mean Age		Sex Distribution		
		Age Range	Mean Age	% Male	% Female	Not Indicated
BUENAVISTA PCF	21	15-72	41	19%	81%	-
JORDAN PCF	15	19-59	38	33%	60%	7%
NUEVA VALENCIA PCF	18	20-64	40	6%	94%	-
SAN LORENZO RHU	23	20-84	46	35%	61%	-
SIBUNAG RHU	19	19-91	51	42%	52%	-
TOTAL	96	15-91	44	21%	71%	2%

Health seeking behavior patterns establish quality-related factors as dominant drivers of facility selection. Figure 7 shows that quality of care and attention from health workers was selected as one of the main considerations for choosing a health facility by 41% of the survey respondents followed by complete and adequate service provision at 25%, while accessibility factors including proximity (15%) and travel time (5%) rank as moderate priorities. The selection of quality-related factors by the majority of the survey population indicates strong patient demand for comprehensive, high-quality primary care services. Furthermore, this encourages investing in healthcare strategies which prioritize a patient’s clinical experience over geographic expansion.

Figure 7. Considerations of patients when selecting a health facility (multiple responses allowed).

Patient Survey: Service Utilization and Access Challenges

Health service utilization from survey data demonstrates strong primary care engagement, with doctor consultations being the highest-accessed service. On average across the 5 PCFs, medical consultations were availed by 78% of survey respondents (Figure 8). Following this was the utilization of laboratory services with 59% and pharmaceutical services at 53% showing moderate utilization. Diagnostic services show a utilization rate of 20% despite substantial community demand. Service availability perception findings reveal gaps in the availability of services with only 51% of patients perceiving all needed services are available within the facility, the other 21% reporting incomplete service availability, and the remaining 27% of the respondents did not provide a response for this field of the survey.

Facility Name	Doctor Consultation	Laboratory Services	Diagnostic Services	Pharmaceutical Services
Buenavista PCF	71%	67%	33%	52%
Jordan PCF	67%	87%	13%	40%
Nueva Valencia PCF	94%	44%	17%	50%
San Lorenzo RHU	83%	57%	22%	65%
Sibunag RHU	74%	47%	11%	53%

■ High (>70%) ■ Medium (40-70%) ■ Low (<40%)

Figure 8. Service utilization heatmap across all the five primary care facilities in the GUHN.

Barriers to health care access and waiting times demonstrate significant prevalence affecting similar population proportions. The distance or proximity of the facility from the patient’s residence affects 53% of patients, followed by unavailability of transportation to go to the facility which affects 30% of the survey population. Health service fees is also a barrier identified by 24% of the patients in accessing care. Having no companion in going to health facilities is considered by 17% of patients while 18% do not have enough information on where to go when needing health services. Identification of these barriers establishes that non-clinical factors influence the access of patients to health services and require interventions from other agencies outside of health. Patient survey results for waiting time (n=67 with complete time data) shows that a patient waits for an average of 91 minutes before care is given, with a median waiting time of 60 minutes or 1 hour. More than half (54%) of the patients experienced waiting times between 30-60 minutes while 30% encountered extended delays and waited for more than 1 to 2 hours (Figure 9). There were 8 patients (12%) who experienced unacceptable delays exceeding two hours while only 16% (n=11) experienced acceptable waiting time under 30 minutes before they are catered in a health facility.

Figure 9. Distribution of wait times when accessing health services from Guimaras PCFs.

Patient Survey: Financial Protection and Patient Satisfaction

Financial protection analysis reveals 66% PhilHealth membership indicating moderate coverage while out-of-pocket (OOP) expense poses a moderate burden to patients during every facility visit. The 80% KONSULTA awareness indicates good benefit knowledge, while actual KONSULTA utilization is only at 56% (Figure 10). The gap between PhilHealth membership and Konsulta awareness shows a 14% gap of missed financial coverage among the survey population. The 24% gap between Konsulta awareness and utilization on the other hand suggests procedural or system barriers preventing full benefit access. Out-of-pocket expense distribution in Figure 11 shows that 41% of patients experiencing no or minimal financial burden (13% no expense, 28% ₱1-₱100 expenses), while 35% face moderate to catastrophic expenses including 31% with moderate burden (₱101-₱500), 4% with high burden (₱501-₱999), and 5% facing catastrophic expenses exceeding ₱1,000.

Figure 10. PhilHealth Membership and Utilization of PhilHealth's Konsulta Benefit Package.

Figure 11. Patient out-of-pocket expense per visit to the health facility.

Patient satisfaction metrics from survey data demonstrate consistently good performance achieving 3.9-4.8 scores on a 5-point scale across all domains. As shown in Figure 12, the province-wide averages are consistently 4.2 for satisfaction with facility staff and health services, and 4.3 for likelihood to recommend the facility. While most individual facilities score close to these averages, Jordan PCF and Nueva Valencia PCF scored slightly above average in satisfaction metrics, while Sibunag RHU scored lower than the average for all three domains and appears to have the most room for improvement. Satisfaction distribution analysis shows 74% high satisfaction (with 4 or 5 rating) across all domains, 22% neutral satisfaction, and 4% low satisfaction (with 1 or 2 rating).

Figure 12. Patient satisfaction survey results.

CAG Assessment: Profile and Service Utilization Perspectives

Community Advisory Group assessment (n=10) provides independent community perspectives with a mean age of 44 and 50% female composition. The CAG members are community leaders and sector representatives who were not actively seeking care during data collection, ensuring unbiased assessment of community health needs and service perceptions. Service utilization patterns of the CAG reveal divergences from patient experiences, with doctor consultation utilization at 80% showing close alignment with patient rates (78%, 2% gap) as shown in Figure 13. Laboratory services demonstrate lower use by community leaders at 50% compared to 59% patient utilization (9% gap), and pharmaceutical services show substantially lower community utilization at 30% versus 53% patient utilization (23% gap).

Figure 13. Comparison of Patient and CAG perspectives in the availability and use of PCF services.

CAG Assessment: Service Quality and Availability

Community perceptions on service availability and satisfaction scores across all domains are notably lower than that of the patients revealing dramatic gaps in awareness and expectation. Only 10% (1 of 10) CAG members perceive that all needed services are available within the facility compared to 51% rate among patient respondents (Figure 13). The 40% gap indicates that community leaders and sector representatives are more aware of service limitations than active patients and have higher expectations for comprehensive service delivery within each PCF. Community quality assessment demonstrates consistently lower satisfaction scores across all dimensions, with CAG staff satisfaction rating at 3.5 compared to patient survey scores of 4.2, service satisfaction at 3.6 versus patient scores of 4.2, and likelihood to recommend at 4.1 compared to patient ratings of 4.3. These expectation gaps indicate that community leaders maintain higher standards for healthcare quality, providing valuable insights for service improvement priorities and realistic expectation management strategies.

CAG Assessment: PhilHealth Coverage and Konsulta Availment

Variances in PhilHealth coverage was noted with CAG members having a higher percentage of PhilHealth members than patient survey respondents. CAG PhilHealth membership rate is at 80% compared to patient survey findings at 66% while awareness about the Konsulta benefit is at 70% versus patient awareness of 80%. This suggests that information may reach community leaders more effectively than community representatives who are not actively utilizing health services. These patterns indicate opportunities for targeted health information sessions for community leaders to

improve demand-supply coordination throughout the network. Such initiatives are also strategic since community leaders have a wide reach and influence that can ensure dissemination of available benefits for the population.

Patient Journey Analysis: Pathway Documentation and Process Efficiency

Patient journey documentation (n=10) reveals standardized care pathways following systematic progression in all primary care facilities. Different stations visited by the patients are those for triage/reception, initial assessment with vital signs collection and primary care consultation, followed by diagnostic support and pharmaceutical services as needed, and discharge/follow-up planning across all facilities (Figure 14). Journey sample characteristics include 73% female representation with mean age of 50 years, distributed across Nueva Valencia (3 cases) and other facilities (2 each), with case types including medical (73%), dental (18%), and pediatric (9%) conditions.

Figure 14. Healthcare pathway for patients within GUHN PCFs.

Process efficiency metrics demonstrate facility-specific variations in waiting times before care is given, with an average waiting time of 26 minutes across the network. Waiting times range from Sibunag's exceptional 2-minute efficiency for a medical consult to a 152-minute wait in Jordan PCF for a follow-up consult to interpret laboratory results. This operational pattern establishes that waiting times vary dramatically across facilities, requiring systematic optimization to ensure equitable service delivery and consistent patient experiences throughout the network.

Patient Journey Analysis: Cost of Care and Operational Bottlenecks

Real-time cost documentation reveals financial risk for patients with only 18% (2 of 11 journeys) having zero-cost episodes. The mean cost of visit to a PCF also reached ₱272.50 which is within the range of survey-reported expenses (Figure 11). Cost component analysis shows free medical consults across all facilities with no registration fees required before accessing care.

Transportation costs range from ₱0-₱200, medication costs at ₱0-₱160³, and diagnostic costs ranging from ₱0-₱1000³ with variable coverage patterns in every facility. While services within the health facility are free, patients continue to incur out-of-pocket expenses for transportation, pharmaceutical, and diagnostic services which they have to access from private providers or public hospitals.

Aside from OOP expenses incurred, operational challenges were also documented which disrupted care pathways. These operational bottlenecks include the absence of a medical doctor on duty at the time of visit, pharmaceutical supply chain disruptions, and lack of laboratory services in-house. One documented case is a patient who had to be deferred from availing a tooth extraction service due to elevated blood pressure. The patient was advised by the dentist to seek medical consultation to check for comorbidities, however at the time of visit, all physicians were out of the facility due to a training call up. The patient was re-scheduled for a follow up three days later, which meant incurring transportation costs to go back to the facility instead of availing the service on the same day.

Patient Journey Analysis: Quality Assessment and Health-seeking Behaviors

Real-time satisfaction measurement from patient journey data shows excellent performance across all domains. Ratings for overall satisfaction and staff communication are both 4.6, ease of navigation at 4.5, facility cleanliness at 4.3, while waiting time satisfaction scores lower at 3.7 (Figure 15). This confirms that operational efficiency represents the primary improvement opportunity within an otherwise high-performing patient experience framework. Process quality evidence demonstrates adaptive care capabilities including wheelchair provision for mobility-challenged patients, patient-centered approaches emphasizing fair treatment ("patient queue is followed and patients are treated fairly"), and responsive service delivery ("quick to attend to patients").

Figure 15. Quality assessment of service provision in primary care facilities.

Community-based care pathway documentation reveals systematic health-seeking behavior of patients before they access healthcare from PCFs (Figure 16). The practice begins with self-care strategies including self-medication ("taking paracetamol and mefenamic acid for fever and pain, respectively") and traditional remedies ("rest, nap for 10 minutes, applying malunggay poultice on affected body part"). This is followed by community consultation networks progressing through family members, barangay health workers, traditional healers ("visiting an albularyo to avail of *pabutbut*

³This range excludes the cost of medicines and diagnostic tests that patients had to pay for after our documentation activity.

ritual⁴"), and formal healthcare facilities as final resort. Facility choice motivations include accessibility ("facility is nearest to our home"), economic necessity ("going to private providers is expensive"), service quality ("quick delivery of services, I like it here"), and financial protection ("it's free"), validating quality-driven healthcare seeking behaviors documented in survey analysis.

Figure 16. Patient health-seeking behavior and community-based care pathway before going to the PCFs.

DISCUSSION

Health System Integration and Strategic Purchasing Effectiveness

The triangulation of facility capacity assessments with multi-method patient experience data, guided by systems thinking principles, reveals critical system integration failures that undermine strategic purchasing effectiveness in small island health systems. The most

significant convergent finding emerges from documented supply constraints creating unmet demand coupled with systematic revenue misallocations that penalize comprehensive primary care delivery. The health financing data provides a glimpse of this strategic purchasing failure: while ₱184.71M is invested for primary health care province-wide, specialized health programs register zero PhilHealth claims across PCFs despite facilities providing TB treatment, family planning, and maternal care services. The finding that 21,024 Guimarasnons registered to public hospital providers receive only 69 services while continuing to frequent PCFs for uncompensated care demonstrates fundamental misalignment between payment and performance.

While the GUHN represents an administratively integrated network model, persistent functional fragmentation undermines the operational integration necessary for effective strategic purchasing. The reliance on outsourced partnerships for essential ancillary services creates care pathways that patients cannot navigate efficiently or affordably, with documented mean costs of ₱272.50 per visit despite supposedly "free" primary care. This fragmentation manifests through operational bottlenecks including absent physicians during training periods and pharmaceutical supply chain disruptions that force patients to incur additional costs and delays. The contrast between Konsulta utilization (₱14.66M across facilities) and complete absence of specialized program revenue demonstrates how current payment mechanisms systematically undermine comprehensive service delivery, creating contradictory incentives that reward fragmented rather than integrated care.

Fragmented information systems extend beyond operational inefficiency to undermine evidence-based strategic purchasing decisions. Multiple encoding requirements across iClinicSys, eKonsulta, FHSIS, PIDSR, ITIS and other required health information systems burden staff with redundant data entry while hindering comprehensive health information analysis necessary for informed resource allocation. This forces provincial health planners to make strategic purchasing decisions based on incomplete information rather than comprehensive population health analysis, systematically undermining the evidence-based decision-making that effective strategic purchasing requires.

⁴ A traditional healing method which involves extraction of foreign objects from the body through rituals.

Regulatory Frameworks and Operational Adaptations for Island Contexts

Real-time patient data collection confirms that quality factors drive facility selection decisions more than accessibility considerations, validating strategic focus on facility licensing and service quality improvements. However, the assessment reveals significant misalignment between national DOH licensing standards and small island operational realities, creating unnecessary barriers while failing to address unique quality assurance challenges that geographic isolation presents. The requirement that San Lorenzo and Sibunag RHUs undergo costly infrastructure renovations to comply with standard floor plans designed for mainland contexts demonstrates how uniform regulatory approaches inadvertently penalize geographic isolation and divert scarce resources from service delivery to compliance activities.

Current licensing standards are prescriptive and fail to recognize alternative quality assurance mechanisms appropriate for island settings. The finding that all five facilities lack licensed pharmacies and clinical laboratories—not due to oversight but due to economic unviability for small catchment populations—supports this claim. The documented reliance on outsourcing arrangements while maintaining basic medicine dispensing under nursing supervision reveals adaptive strategies that balance regulatory compliance with practical service delivery needs, suggesting opportunities for performance-based standards that focus on health outcomes rather than structural requirements.

Supply-side workforce analysis integrated with real-time process documentation reveals how staffing constraints manifest as operational bottlenecks with substantial efficiency variations. Journey documentation shows stark waiting time variations—from Sibunag's 2-minute efficiency to Jordan PCF's 152-minute wait— while supply-side analysis identifies critical workforce gaps including absent pharmacists across all facilities and dependence on contractual nursing staff. The documented dependence on contractual staff and DOH deployments creates a precarious foundation for health system strengthening that threatens sustainability of capacity-building investments, with rapid staff turnover negating training investments and creating unsustainable pressure on existing personnel. Adequate physician coverage despite process inefficiencies in the facilities suggests that workforce quality compensates for quantity limitations, but this adaptation strategy is unsustainable when key personnel are unavailable during training periods.

Community Engagement and Quality-Equity Balance

The Community Advisory Group assessment reveals community health system awareness that provides a strong foundation for meaningful governance participation. CAG members consistently maintain higher quality expectations than active patients as demonstrated through lower satisfaction scores across all domains and more critical service availability assessments. This indicates that community leaders possess analytical capability and independence necessary for effective health system accountability while maintaining realistic but demanding quality standards that reflect broader population expectations.

Current patient experience data may underestimate true community needs by capturing primarily experiences of those with sufficient resources and motivation to access care, potentially missing perspectives of populations facing greatest access challenges. The finding that quality factors outweigh accessibility considerations validates quality improvement investments, but may inadvertently create access barriers for population segments who cannot prioritize quality over proximity due to transportation costs, time constraints, or competing economic pressures. Health financing data supports this concern: transportation costs ranging from ₱0-₱200 per visit, combined with 53% of patients identifying distance as a barrier to care, suggests quality-driven facility selection represents privilege available primarily to patients with sufficient resources to absorb travel costs and time investments. This quality-access trade-off has significant implications for strategic purchasing, as payment mechanisms based on patient satisfaction scores may systematically undervalue service

improvements necessary to reach underserved populations, potentially perpetuating rather than addressing health inequities.

Documented systematic health-seeking behavior pathways reveal well-established community health governance networks that strategic purchasing mechanisms can leverage to improve both accountability and cultural appropriateness of care delivery. The finding that 80% of CAG members maintain PhilHealth membership compared to 66% of the general population, combined with their superior awareness of service gaps, indicates that community leaders possess both health financing literacy and system knowledge necessary for meaningful participation in strategic purchasing decisions that extend beyond consultation to include provider performance monitoring and resource allocation input.

Implementation Strategy and Systemic Reform Requirements

The GUHN requires fundamental adaptations to national frameworks rather than simple scaling of mainland approaches to achieve Universal Health Care implementation. While the province demonstrates strong foundational elements—80% PhilHealth coverage, universal Konsulta accreditation, high patient satisfaction scores, and sophisticated community governance capacity—documented structural limitations reveal that current strategic purchasing mechanisms inadequately address inherent island health system constraints. The documented geographic premium for health care averaging ₱272.50 per visit with 35% facing moderate-to-catastrophic expenses creates systematic financial protection failures that undermine UHC implementation objectives.

Network-based strategic purchasing that treats GUHN as a single contracting unit represents the most critical reform necessary to address revenue fragmentation and service integration challenges. This approach would align payment incentives with integrated care pathways while incorporating external partnership costs into comprehensive payment bundles that transform current patient cost burdens into systematic financial protection. The integration of transportation subsidies, external laboratory and pharmacy costs, and diagnostic service access into risk-adjusted capitation rates could eliminate the geographic penalties that currently undermine financial protection objectives, supported by evidence that facilities provide comprehensive services but cannot access appropriate revenue streams for TB treatment, family planning, and maternal care. Strategic private sector complementation for laboratory, diagnostic, and pharmaceutical services can be formalized within this network-based approach to ensure seamless service delivery while maintaining appropriate controls for quality standards and cost considerations.

Context-adapted regulatory standards that focus on health outcomes rather than structural compliance requirements represent the second critical reform area. The high patient satisfaction scores despite documented service gaps indicates that communities distinguish between regulatory compliance and service quality in ways that current licensing frameworks do not capture. Performance-based standards that maintain safety objectives while acknowledging legitimate operational constraints could redirect resources from compliance activities to service delivery improvements, potentially addressing the diagnostic service gaps that represent the most significant unmet need documented in the assessment.

Enhanced community governance mechanisms that leverage existing social capital provide the third essential component for sustainable UHC implementation in island settings. The sophisticated health-seeking behavior networks, combined with demonstrated community leadership capacity and quality-driven healthcare preferences, create foundation for accountability mechanisms that extend beyond patient satisfaction measurement to include broader population health advocacy and strategic purchasing oversight. The documented preference for quality improvements over geographic expansion, supported by community willingness to absorb moderate transportation costs

for superior care, suggests that communities will support governance reforms that prioritize service enhancement and accountability strengthening, providing the political foundation necessary for implementing governance arrangements that meaningfully integrate community voices into health system decision-making processes.

Financial protection strengthening through comprehensive PhilHealth enrollment and enhanced Konsulta registration, combined with community engagement strategies focusing on information flow improvement and expectation alignment dialogue, represents the foundational work necessary to support these systemic reforms. However, the assessment demonstrates that operational improvements in diagnostic service delivery, process efficiency standardization, and community-responsive service enhancement require the broader policy reforms outlined above to achieve sustainable impact. This integrated analysis confirms that while the GUHN possesses the foundational elements necessary for Universal Health Care implementation, realizing equitable, people-centered, and responsive primary healthcare for all Guimarasnons requires systematic adaptation of national UHC frameworks to acknowledge and address the unique challenges and opportunities that small island health systems present.

CONCLUSION

This comprehensive assessment has successfully generated evidence-based insights necessary in enhancing the capacity of the GUHN to deliver equitable, people-centered, and safe primary health care services to all Guimarasnons. Through systematic triangulation of facility capacity assessments, patient experience documentation, and community stakeholder engagement, this evaluation guided by systems thinking principles provides the foundational evidence needed for informed decision-making and strategic innovation in primary health care strengthening, that address unique structural challenges while leveraging distinctive community assets.

Focused specifically on deep-diving into primary care facility capacities within the GUHN, and as such this assessment does not comprehensively address the critical role of hospitals that deliver secondary and tertiary care services. While the provincial hospital and the two district hospitals are integral components of the care continuum and essential for managing complex cases requiring inpatient care, this evaluation concentrated on the five PCFs that serve as the first contact of care for Guimarasnons. The documented referral patterns and care pathways acknowledge the important interconnections between PCFs and hospital services, but a comprehensive understanding of the entire GUHN network would require additional assessment of hospital capacities, inpatient service delivery, and secondary-primary care coordination mechanisms.

A central finding of this assessment shows that the GUHN possesses the foundational elements for UHC implementation but faces systemic barriers that national frameworks do not adequately address. The province has achieved remarkable success in building health system infrastructure and community engagement, yet persistent gaps in service integration, financial protection, and regulatory alignment prevent the translation of these strengths into comprehensive primary care access. This paradox—strong foundations undermined by framework misalignment—suggests that the path forward requires policy innovation rather than intensified implementation of existing approaches.

This assessment offers three critical insights for health systems strengthening in island contexts. First, geographic isolation creates unavoidable cost premiums that conventional financing mechanisms cannot address, requiring risk-adjusted payment models that acknowledge transportation and service delivery constraints. Second, community governance capacity in island settings often exceeds that of mainland contexts, providing opportunities for sophisticated health system stewardship that current governance frameworks underutilize. Third, the quality-driven

health-seeking behaviors documented across all population groups create strong demand for service improvements, suggesting that communities will support governance reforms that prioritize accountability and service enhancement.

These findings have immediate implications for national UHC policy development and implementation in similar contexts across the Philippines. The documented strategic purchasing deficiency and regulatory misalignments affecting Guimaras likely affect other small island provinces. This suggests that successful UHC implementation requires systematic policy adaptations for geographic and demographic contexts rather than uniform national approaches. The presence of community health governance networks identified also provide a replicable model for meaningful community participation in health system design and accountability.

Moving forward, the GUHN is positioned to serve as a learning site for developing and testing innovative approaches to island health system strengthening. The comprehensive evidence base generated through this assessment, combined with demonstrated community commitment and governance capacity, creates optimal conditions for prototyping integrated service delivery models, community-responsive governance mechanisms, and sustainable financing innovations. Success in implementing these innovations in Guimaras will provide valuable evidence for scaling effective approaches to other island contexts while contributing to broader understanding of how health systems can adapt to serve diverse geographic and demographic populations effectively.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Building on the evidence generated and anchoring on the opportunity for Guimaras as a learning site for island health system innovation, we recommend implementing an Innovation Prototyping Framework that transforms documented challenges into testable solutions through iterative design and stakeholder co-creation. This proposed intervention addresses the central paradox identified in the GUHN, as having strong foundational capacity undermined by framework misalignment, through three interconnected prototype tracks that leverage existing GUHN strengths while testing innovative approaches to persistent challenges. Each prototype track operates through a 15-18 months rapid-cycle testing with continuous stakeholder feedback and adaptive modifications based on real-time learning.

PROTOTYPE TRACK 1: Integrated Service Delivery Network

Timeline: 18 months | Lead: Provincial Health Officer

Innovation Objective: Transform fragmented facility-based care into coordinated network-based service delivery that optimizes resources and improves patient experiences across the entire island.

Key Prototyping Elements:

- **Hub-and-Spoke Service Coordination:** Redesign service delivery to leverage facility-specific strengths while ensuring comprehensive care access from any entry point, testing solutions to documented service gaps
- **Unified Patient Care Pathways:** Create seamless care experiences that coordinate consultation, diagnostic, pharmaceutical, and referral services regardless of patient registration location, prototyping solutions to strategic purchasing deficiencies
- **Mobile Service Integration:** Pilot rotating specialist and diagnostic services that bring comprehensive care to patients, testing approaches to reduce documented geographic cost premiums
- **Shared Resource Optimization:** Test resource sharing models that maximize utilization of equipment, personnel, and expertise across the network

PROTOTYPE TRACK 2: Community-Responsive Health Governance

Timeline: 15 months | Lead: Community Advisory Group Coordinators

Innovation Objective: Design and test governance mechanisms that enable meaningful community participation in health system design and accountability while leveraging existing social capital, traditional health practices, and community health awareness.

Key Prototyping Elements:

- **Community Health System Stewardship:** Establish governance structures that give communities meaningful authority over health system priorities and resource allocation decisions
- **Real-Time Feedback Integration:** Prototype mechanisms that continuously adapt health service delivery based on community needs and satisfaction
- **Traditional-Modern Health Integration:** Consider protocols that formally integrate traditional healing practices with modern primary care services
- **Community Health Financing Innovation:** Test cooperative models that pool community resources for transportation, supplemental medications, and enhanced services

PROTOTYPE TRACK 3: Sustainable Island Health Financing

Timeline: 18 months | Lead: Provincial Health Board

Innovation Objective: Develop and test financing mechanisms that ensure comprehensive primary care access while addressing the unique cost structures and resource constraints of island health systems.

Key Prototyping Elements:

- **Network-Based Strategic Purchasing:** Strengthen payment mechanisms that treat the entire GUHN as a single health system rather than competing individual facilities
- **Integrated External Service Financing:** Create models that incorporate external laboratory, diagnostic, and pharmaceutical costs into comprehensive primary care payment bundles
- **Geographic Risk Adjustment:** Prototype capitation mechanisms that account for island-specific costs and ensure financial sustainability

The proposed prototyping implementation strategy employs a human-centered design approach that emphasizes stakeholder co-creation, rapid testing, and iterative refinement. Collaborative design workshops involving the Project Core Team, Community Advisory Board, and Provincial Health Board initiates this approach towards consensus on the prototype tracks, followed by rapid-cycle design and testing. This approach also demands substantial monitoring and stakeholder feedback mechanisms that allows for continuous adaptation based on progress inputs.

Implementation experiences and outcomes from this prototyping approach will provide the Philippine health system with an island context model for delivering equitable, people-centered primary healthcare while contributing to global understanding of how local health systems can adapt to serve diverse geographic and demographic populations effectively. The approach also demonstrates how technical assistance can evolve from conventional implementation support to collaborative innovation partnerships that generate actionable insights for health system strengthening. Success in Guimaras will show that small island health systems can achieve Universal Health Care goals through innovative approaches that acknowledge and address unique contextual challenges while leveraging distinct community assets. This offers a potentially replicable pathway for transforming both health system delivery and technical assistance methodologies in similar settings throughout the archipelago and beyond.

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